

**Yakin Zaune: Finafinai a Matsayin Makaman Yakar
Tunanin Al'umma (Kalubale Ga Hausawa)**

The Silent Fight: Films as Tools for Propaganda (A Challenge to the Hausas)

Na

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Abstract

Previous researches have proven the relationship between literature and human thoughts. Films are, however, among the modern works of literature that have great significance on human behaviors. Films are largely accepted and watching films has become a tradition to almost all communities in the world. Therefore, it is not surprising that films are used as tools for propaganda. Accordingly, this paper is set to examine the relevance of films as tools for propaganda in disseminating and imposing ideologies to large targeted populations. The paper analyses films produced in some selected countries to determine the extent to which the films display the caliber of development of those countries which ranges from political, social, to developments in the areas of science and technology. On the other hand, the paper studies some Hausa films to ascertain if they promote the cultural heritage and display the good sides of the socio-political practices of the Hausas. The paper hypothesized that the Hausa films usually downgrade the status of the Hausas and Nigeria in general instead of promoting them. Marxism Film Theory is used in the study. Data were collected from interviews and critical studies of some selected films. The study found out that, the Hausa films are lacking in promoting Hausa culture. In conclusion, the paper proposed some suggestions as a panacea to the current shortcomings of the Hausa films. One of them is that the Hausa filmmakers should work hand-in-hand with Hausa resource persons in providing good film contents.

Key Words: Films, Hausas, Culture, Propaganda, Marxism

Tsakure

Masana da marubuta da dama, sun tabbatar da dangantakar adabi da tunanin al'umma a cikin rubuce-rubucensu mabambanta. Finafinai na ɗaya daga cikin rukunnen adabin zamani da ya samu karbuwa tare da mamaye zukatan jama'a. Za a iya cewa, fim a duniyar yau, tamkar ruwan dare ne wanda ya karadè dukkan nahiyoyi. Lura da haka, bai zama abin mamaki ba, yayin da gwamnatocin kasashen da suka bunkasa ke amfani da masana'antun finafinan da ke karkashinsu, domin yada sakonnin da suka shafi manufofi da muradunsu da cigabansu, har ma da farfagandar ruruta karfin iko da suke da shi. A bisa wannan matashiya ne makalar ta kudiri aniyar bitar tasirin finafinai wajen daukaka matsayin al'umma a idon duniya. Makalar ta bibiyi wasu finafinan ketare domin bayyana yadda irin waɗannan kasashe ke amfani da finafinai wajen daukaka matsayinsu da nuna fasaharsu. A bangare ɗaya kuwa, makalar ta dubi wasu finafinan Hausa domin duba yadda lamarin yake. A hasashen wannan bincike, sau da dama finafinan Hausa na dakushe martaba da fikrar Hausawa da ma Nijeriya baki ɗaya, a maimakon daukaka darajarsu da fasaharsu. Ra'in da aka gina takardar a kai shi ne makisanci (Marxism). Makalar ta yi amfani da Ra'in Makisancin Fim (Marxism Film Theory) wajen nazartar wasu finafinai da suka hada da na Hausa da kuma na ketare. Sannan an yi amfani da salon hira a matsayin hanyar samun bayanar da aka gina sakamakon binciken kansu. Binciken ya gano cewa, an bar finafinan Hausa a baya wajen kokarin bunkasa al'ada da bayyana ci gaban kasar Hausa. Daga karshe takardar ta ba da shawarwari. Daya daga cikinsu shi ne, masu shirya finafinai su yi aiki hannu da hannu tare da masana Hausa domin gano inda za a yi a tufkar hanci.

Muhimman kalmomi: Finafinai, Hausawa, Al'ada, Farfaganda, Makisanci

1.0 Gabatarwa

Finafinai na daya daga cikin rukunnen adabin zamani da ke da matuƙar tasiri a tsakanin al'umma a duniyar yau. Fage, (2004) yana da ra'ayin cewa, finafinai a yau sun zama wani ɓangare na rayuwar al'umma. Kusan za a iya cewa, babu wata al'ummar da ta samu cigaba a faɗin duniya a yau, face sai tana cudanya da finafinan da take samarwa, ko waɗanda ke shigo mata daga baƙin al'ummu, ko kuma ma duka biyun. Kafin bunƙasar finafinai a zamanance, madidinsu sun kasance wasannin kwaikwayon gargajiya. *Wasa da satar kama* ke haɗuwa su ba da wasan kwaikwayo, wanda kuma ake gudanarwa musamman domin cim ma ɗaya ko fiye daga cikin waɗannan manufofi:

- i. Koyar da tarbiyya
- ii. Hannunka mai sanda ko faɗakarwa
- iii. Nuna wata al'ada
- iv. Ilimantarwa
- v. Nishaɗantarwa da makamantansu

A kasar Hausa, finafinan farko sun ɗauki wannan layi, inda ake bin addini da al'adar Bahaushe yayin samar da su. Abin tambaya a nan shi ne, ko yaya abin yake a yau?

A ɓangare guda kuwa, finafinan kasarshen ketare suna amfani da su matsayin babbar hanyar farfaganda. Ta cikin irin waɗannan finafinai ne suke yadɗa manufofinsu tare da kare martabarsu da daga darajarsu da kuma kambama ƙarfin ikonsu. Wannan takarda za ta yi ƙoƙarin hasko yadda abin ke kasancewa a finafinan ketare tare kuma da dubawa ko akan samu irin haka a finafinan Hausa?

1.1 Matsala

Tun a shekarar (2004), Muhammad ya ja hankali dangane da farfaganda cikin finafinan duniya a ƙarshen bincikensa inda yake cewa: “Siyasar duniya ta harkar fim yanzu kowa ya rungume ta, don haka dole mu tashi daga barci don an yi mana nesa a wannan fagen” (Muhammad, 2004: 475). A cikin finafinan Hausa kuwa, ko bayan batun saba wa al'ada da rashin hankalci mai kyau ga al'umma a matsayin madubin hasko rayuwarsu, wani abin tambaya kullum shi ne, ‘shin ma labarin masu shirya fim ɗin Hausa, yaya suka samar da shi, ko satacce ne daga finafinan ketare?’

Hakan kuma, ya sanya da dama daga cikin Hausawa sun gwammace su kalli finafinan kasashen ketare a maimakon na Hausa. Ba wai don ba sa son kallon na Hausan ba, sai don abin da jakin dawa ya fada yayin da ya ga na gida: “Allah wadarai naka ya lalace.” Lallai ke nan, akwai bukatar a yi binciken abin da ya shafi nau’o’in farfaganda na finafinan duniya da kuma duba inda aka kwana cikin finafinan Hausa. Ana sa ran hakan zai zama wata fitilar haskawa ko hannunka-mai-sanda ga wafanda abin ya shafa.

1.2 Muradin Bincike

Wannan makala ta mayar da hankali ne kan nazartar tasirin da finafinai ke da shi kan tunanin al’umma, wanda hakan ya sa kasashe da dama ke amfani da su a matsayin babban makamin farfaganda. Kai tsaye takardar tana kofarin cim ma manyan muradu guda uku:

- i. Waiwayen tasirin finafinai a kan tunanin al’umma.
- ii. Fito da yadda kasashen ketare ke amfani da finafinai a matsayin farfaganda domin daga daraja da yada manufofinsu.
- iii. Nazartar hoton fikirar Hausawa cikin finafinan Hausa.

1.3 Dabarun Bincike

Wannan takarda to doru a kan wasu dabarun bincike domin cim ma muradunta. Dabarun sun hada da zaɓen ra’in da za a dora binciken a kai da hanyar da za a bi domin samun bayanana da za a gina sakamakon bincike a kai, tare kuma da iyakance farfajiyar da binciken zai yawata a ciki.

1.3.1 Ra’in Bincike

An dora wannan aiki a kan ra’in Makisanci. Wannan ra’in ya samo asali ne daga baban malamin falsafa mai suna *Karl Marx*. Ra’in ya samu tun kimanin karni na goma sha takwas (18K), wanda kuma babban muradinsa ya kasance fafutukar dakile zalunci da cin zalin da mai karfi ke yi wa na kasa da shi. Bayan shudewar lokaci, malaman falsafa sun riƙa sauya wa kalmar Makisanci ma’ana.¹ Wannan ya danganci muhallin da aka yi amfani da ra’in, wato ko dai a siyasa ne, ko zamantakewa, ko kasuwanci, ko addini da makamantansu.

¹ A bisa wannan dalili ne Karogal (ed) (1999: 122) yake cewa: “Eben though the term 'Mardism' gives a certain sense, there are so many shades of meaning included in it.” Fassara: “Duk da cewa kalmar Makisanci na ba da ma’ana ta musamman, akwai wasu ma’anoni da dama da ke tattare da ita.”

Har ila yau, ra'in yana nuna cewa, ya kamata kuma ya zama dole finafinan kowace al'ummu su samu damar bayyana muradunsu ga duniya kamar yadda abin yake a manyan kasashen da ke da ikon fada-a-ji. Idan muka dora manufar takardar kan wannan ra'in, za mu samar da ma'anar cewa, ya kamata finafinan Hausa su dukufa wajen daukaka darajar al'ummar da suke wakilta (Hausawa) a idon duniya. Wannan zai yiwu ne ta hanyar nuna wa duniya irin fasahohinsu da fikirarsu na zahiri da ma na kambamar zulake.

1.3.2 Hanyoyin Tattara Bayanai

Wannan bincike ya takaita ne ga finafinai kawai. An nazarci wasu finafinan Hausa da kuma na kasashen ketare, domin samun bayanai da za su taimaka wajen cimma muradin wannan bincike. A bangare guda kuma, an tattauna da wasu masu kallon irin waɗannan finafinai, domin kara samun haske da tabbaci kan nazarin da takardar ta yi a karan kanta (na kallon kwaƙƙwafi ga finafinai). An tanadi tambayoyi na musamman waɗanda a kansu ne aka gina hirarrakin da aka yi. Ana sa ran sakamakon binciken ya kasance ya daidaita da zahiri, sannan ya zamana mai ba da gudummawa wurin inganta harkar finafinan Hausa.

2.0 Waiwaye

Ko kusa wannan bai kasance aiki na farko ba, da aka gudanar game da finafinan Hausa da kuma musamman finafinai a matakin duniya gaba ɗaya. Saboda haka ne wannan bangare na takardar zai dukufa wajen zakulo ra'ayoyin wasu ayyukan da suka gabata a wannan bangare, musamman dangane da tasirin finafinai a kan tunanin al'umma da rayuwarsu ta gaba ɗaya. Sannan za a waiwayi inda aka fito da kuma inda ake a yau dangane da finafinan Hausa.

2.1 Matsayin Adabi A Duniya: Gurbin Finafinai

Kamar yadda adabi ya kasance madubi ko wani hoto na duba rayuwar al'umma, a koyaushe ana kyautata zaton adabin al'umma ya kasance mai wakiltar wannan al'umma. Wannan kuwa zai samu ne yayin da su al'ummar suka yi yunkurin bayyana hoton kansu cikin adabinsu, ko kuma ma ba tare da sun yi wani yunkurin yin hakan ba. Hakan kuwa na faruwa ne a sakamakon tasirin muhalli ga tunani da hikimomin ɗan'adam.

Akwai masana da suke da ra'ayin cewa, finafinai sun wuce "shiri kawai." A maimakon haka, sun kasance ne "labaran gaskiya da aka taskance cikin hikima." (Arnheim, 1997: 8). Masu wannan

ra'ayi sun dogara kan cewa, fim ya kasance tamkar hoton da aka zana da hannu. Shi kuwa zane, ya dogara ne kai tsaye da abubuwan da idanun mai yin sa ke kallo. Saboda haka, abin da ake tsammani shi ne, duk wani lamarin da ya faru a cikin fim, haka abin yake ko dai a zahiri, ko a tunanin masu shirin fim dɓn. Yazdani ya rawaito Mark yana cewa:

Whether we like it or not, our most profound thoughts and most intimate secrets, are now constantly expressed and experienced via moving pictures on screens big and small.

Fassara

Ko mu yarda ko kar mu yarda, a yanzu ana nuna mafi girman tunaninmu da sirrukanmu a kan fuskar talabijin a matsayin hotuna masu motsi manya da kanana. (Mark a cikin Yazdani ND: 21).

Pirkis, Blood, Francis, da McCallum (2005), sun yi wani gagarumin bincike da ya shafi bibiyar ayyukan da aka gudanar game da tasirin finafinai kan rayuwar al'umma ta zahiri. Sun mayar da hankali wurin gano "ko kisan kai da ake nunawa cikin finafinai na da tasiri a kan al'umma?" Sakamakon binciken nasu ya nuna cewa, ko da ba a samu tasiri na kai tsaye ba, haƙiƙa akwai misalan lokutan da aka aiwatar da kisan kai daidai da yadda aka taɓa nunawa cikin wani fim. Bisa wannan ne ma suka ba da shawara da cewa:

Mental health professionals and suicide experts should collaborate with film makers and television producers to try to balance entertainment against the risk of harm, and to promote opportunities for education. (Pirkis, Blood, Francis, da McCallum, 2005: 2).

Fassara:

Ya kamata likitocin kwakwalwa da masana kan harkar kisan kai su hada guiwa da masu shirya finafinai domin garan bawul a harkar fim yadda za a tsallake jefa masu kallo cikin hadari, sannan a inganta ilimantarwa da ke ciki.

Daga maganar tasu, za a iya fahimtar ra'ayinsu ya karkata kan cewa, finafinai na da tasiri a kan tunanin dɓn'adam, wanda har na iya sanya mutum aikata wani abu da ya gani cikin fim. Wannan kuwa ya yi daidai da binciken (Phillips, 1982) inda ya gano cewa, an samu rahotannin kisan kai a wasu satuka da suka kasance a jere a shekarar 1977 cikin Tarayyar Amurka a sakamakon sigar labari da ke kunshe da kisan kai wanda aka yi wa suna da "Soap Opera Stories."

Sbardellati, (2012: 43) ya rawaito A. P. Giannini inda karara yake nuni da matuƙar tasirin finafinai. Yana cewa: “*The nation which controls the cinema can control the thought of the world*” Ma’ana: “Duk kasar da za ta iya sarrafa sinima, to za ta iya sarrafa tunanin duniya.” Wannan magana ta zama sha-kundum dangane da batun da ake yi. Ta kai matuƙa wajen nuni ga tasirin finafinai a kan tunanin al’umma. Ba makawa, Giannini ya yi la’akari ne da yadda farfagandar fim ke tasiri a zukata, wanda bisa wannan fahimta ne ya yi wannan furuci.

Muhammad, (2004) na da irin wannan ra’ayi, inda yake cewa: “Wasu kasashe a duniya suna fim ne don su yadda manufofinsu a siyasance a cikin hikima ga al’ummar duniya yadda mutum zai ji yana son wannan akidar”. (Muhammad, 2004: 475).

Finafinai a matsayin wani ɓangare na adabin baka ya samu karbuwa da bunkasa matuƙa. Hakan ya ja hankalin al’ummu da dama da suka haɗa da gwamnatocin kasashen inda suke amfani da su wajen yadda manufofinsu. Akwai muhimman ɓangarorin rayuwa da finafinan kasashen duniya suka fi mayar da hankali. A kasa an tattauna wasu daga ciki:

i. Bajintar Jami’an Tsaro: Tsaro na da matuƙar muhimmanci wanda na daya daga cikin abubuwan da ke nuna matsayin cigaba tare da karfin ikon Kasa. A bisa wannan dalili ne kasashen duniya da dama ke amfani da finafinai domin kambama karfin tsaro da suke da shi. Wannan ya haɗa da nuna dimbin kayan yaƙi na zamani da suke da shi, tare kuma da jaruman matakan tsaro masu bajinta da jajircewa. A wani fim na kasar Indiya mai suna *Main Hoon Surya Singham*, an yi koƙarin nuna irin nagartar ‘yan sandan Indiya, har da kambamar zulafke.

A cikin wannan hoto, ‘yansandan kasar Afirka ta Kudu tare da wani dansandan kasar Indiya na bin wani dan ta’adda da gudu. Kamar walkiya dansandan kasar Indiya ya wuce su.

Daga karshe kawai, sai ‘yan sandan kasar Afirka ta Kudu suka saki baki suna mamakin irin kwarewa da jarumta da bajintar wannan d’ansanda na kasar Indiya.

ii. Fikira da Kaifin Basirar Jami’an Tsaro: Akwai kuma finafinai da dama da ke nuna kaifin basira na jami’an tsaron irin waɗannan kasashe da ke shirya finafinan. Wannan wani salo ne na yin barazana a sauran kasashen duniya ta hanyar nuna cewa, kasar, a shirye take da ta daƙile duk wani aikin ta’addanci da za a iya yi wa kasar barazana da shi. An nuna irin wannan a wani fim na kasar Sin, mai suna: *Who Am I*. A ciki an gwada tsantsar basirar jami’an tsaro na *C.I.A.* inda suka yi binciken farkashin kasa dangane da d’aya daga cikin manyan ma’aikatansu da suke tuhuma da gurbacewar zuciya da ta kai shi ga almundahana. Daga karshe kuwa suka gano shi, sannan suka yi masa kofar rago lokacin da yake kofarin tserewa daga babban ofishinsu na tsaro. Yayin da mai kallo ya bibiyi wannan fim, dole ya jinjina wa jami’an *C.I.A.* na kasar Sin, duk kuwa da ya san cewa shiri ne.

Kifi na ganin ka... Bayan ya kare gudunsa, sai ga shi kewaye da jami’an tsaro ta ko’ina. Jami’ai na tafe a kasa, ga wasu jikin jiragen yaki, haka ma wasu na cikin jiragen ruwa a tafkin da ke gefen hanya.

iii. Son Kasa: Akwai finafinan kasashen duniya da dama da aka gina a kan jigon son kasa tare da yi mata aiki tukuri. Hakika irin waɗannan finafinai na taimakawa wajen cusa kishin kasa ga zukatan ‘yan kasa, tare da yi musu kaimi wajen kofarin yin hidima ga kasarsu. An nuna irin wannan a wani fim na Indiya mai suna: *Knock Out*.

Duk da ana amfani da shi domin badaƙalar dukiyar kasa, da taimakon wani jami'in tsaron kasarsu ya shiryu kuma ya mayar da maƙuden kuɗin da aka sata. Wannan ya sa al'umma suka tarbe shi tamkar wani annabi.

ib. Baiwa: A film ɗin *Abengers Infinity War*, an nuna yadda ƙasar Amurka ke da al'umma masu ɗimbin baiwa. Sannan a fim ɗin an nuna irin waɗannan mutanen shirye suke da su kare ƙasarsu tare ma da duniya baki ɗaya. A cikin irin kambamar zulaƙe da aka yi wa irin baiwarsu, har an nuna yadda suka ƙalubalanci wasu halittu da suka sauko daga wata duniya ta daban, waɗanda kuma sun kasance masu tsananin ƙarfin tuwo da ƙarfin tsafi.

Jaruman suka tinkari waɗannan halittu masu ban tsoro da tsananin ƙarfi. Duk da cewa shiri ne kawai, hakan na ƙara nuni da tsagwaron bajintar masu shirya wannan fim.

6. Wanke Kai Daga Zargi: Kasashen duniya na amfani da finafinai domin wanke kansu daga wani zargi da ake musu. Sau da dama akan alaƙanta ayyukan ta'addanci da Musulunci. A wani fim mai suna: *Tiger*, jarumar fim ɗin ta wanke ƙasar Pakistan, (wadda ta kasance mafi yawan mazaunanta Musulmai ne), daga alaƙanta su da aikin ta'addanci da duniya take yi. A cikin fim ɗin an nuna cewa, ta'addanci ya kasance tamkar sana'a ce tsakanin 'yan ta'adda da kuma munafukan ɗaiɗaikun mutane daga ƙasashen duniya.

“Because of a few troublemakers, my country is misunderstood by the world.”

Fassara:

“Duniya ta yi muna mummunan fahimta a dalilin wasu tsirarun tsageru.”

vi. Adana Muhimman Tarihi: Wannan ma wani babban jigo ne da ake samu daga finaifinan ketare. Akan samu wani muhimmin tarihi a yi masa kwaskwarima da dadin gishiri yadda zai kasance mai kayatarwa tare da jan hankali. Irin wannan tarihi na shiga zukatan masu kallo ya zauna daram. Za a iya cewa, babbar hanyar adana tarihi ce tare da yadda shi ga al’ummun duniya. Za mu iya samun irin wannan misali a fim mai suna, *Fele: Birth of A Legend*. Wannan fim ne na kasar Amurka, inda aka adana tarihin wani fitaccen dan kwallon kasar Birazil mai suna Pele.

vii. Hasashen Gobe: Finaifinan ketare ba su tsaya kan abubuwan da suka gabata ko wadanda da ake ciki a duniyar yau kawai ba. A maimakon haka, sukan yi hasashen yadda gobe za ta kasance. Sukan yi hakan domin nuna wata musiba da ka iya aukuwa a sakamakon wani abu, ko kuma wani ci gaban zamani da za a iya samu. A bisa wannan ne, Hjort ke cewa: *“Film... has an extraordinary capacity to expand our reality.”* Fassara: Shirin fim... na da matuƙar tasiri wurin inganta al’amuran rayuwarmu ta haƙiƙa.” (Hjort in Yazdani, ND: 25).

A fim din hadin guiwa tsakanin kasashen Amurka da Sin mai suna: *The Great Wall*, an yi matuƙar koƙari wurin hasashen girman matsalar da duniya za ta iya fuskanta daga Yajuju da Majuju. Yajuju da Majuju dai wasu halittu ne sanannu ga Hausawa, musamman kasancewar Alkur’ani ya kawo maganarsu. A cikin wannan fim, an nuna cewa, dakarun kasar Sin ne ke ta koƙarin kare duniya daga sharrin wadannan halittu na tsawon shekaru barkatai. Sai kuma aka nuna irin musibar da za ta iya aukuwa yayin da suka samu damar shigowa duniya.

viii. Kimiyya da Fasaha: Finaifinan ketare suna mai da hankali matuƙa game da kimiyya da fasaha. Sukan yi haka domin nuna wa duniya matuƙa da suka kai a bangaren kere-kere. Kasar da ta yi fice ga fasahar kere-kere za ta kasance tana da karfin dogaro da kanta tare kuma da samar

da makamai irin na zamani. Wadannan kuwa na daga cikin manyan abubuwan da ke ba wa kasa karfin iko a idon duniya.

2.2 Finafinan Hausa

Masana da manazarta da dama sun yi rubuce-rubuce mabambanta dangane da samuwa da bunkasar finafinan Hausa. Komawa kan wannan batu zai kasance tamkar maimaici ne kawai.² Sai dai duk da haka, akwai muhimman abubuwan da tarihin finafinan Hausa ba zai manta da su ba. Sun hada da:

- i. An fara fim na farko a Nijeriya karkashin kulawar Herbert Macaulay a shekarar 1903 (Ali, 2004). Wannan ya faru tun kafin kafuwar Nijeriya a matsayin kasa guda, wanda hakan bai wakana ba sai a shekarar 1914.
- ii. Finafinan Hausa kuwa an fara su ne tsakanin shekarar 1980 zuwa 1984 a Kano (Gidan Dabino, 2001). A hankali ne wadannan finafinai suka ci gaba da bunkasa tare da samun sauye-sauye sakamakon karin ilimi da wayewa da kuma zamananci, har dai suka kai sigar da ake kallon su a yau.
- iii. A shekarar 1990 ne finafinan Hausa (wandanda a lokacin an fi kiran su da finafinan Kanawa) suka samu karbuwa. A wannan shekara ne kuma aka samu fitattun kungiyoyin shirya finafinai guda uku wato (Gwauron Dutse da Gyaranya da kuma Karate).
- iv. A karkashin wadannan kungiyoyi, Alhaji Hamisu da Muhammad Gurgu da Sani Lamma sun dauki nauyin samar da finafinai uku da suka shahara a wancan lokaci (*Hukuma Maganin 'Yan Banza* da *'Yan Daukar Amarya* da kuma *Bakar Indiya*). Wadannan finafinai sun taka rawa matuka wajen fito da harkar fim fili tare da kara cusa karbuwarsu ga zukatan jama'a.

A zuwa yau, kusan kowane sati sai an fitar da sabbin finafinan Hausa. Garuruwan da aka fi shirya irin wadannan finafinai su ne Kano da Kaduna da kuma Jos. Akwai kampunna da dama da suke daukar nauyin shirya finafinen. Sun hada da:

² Dumbin rubuce-rubucen da aka yi dangane da finafinan Hausa sun hada da: Gidan Dabino, (2001); Aminu, (2002); Ali, (2004); Fage, (2004); Abdullahi da Maidabino, (2013); Danmaigoro, (2013); Kiyawa, (2013) da sauransu.

S/N	Sunan Kampanin Fim	Jaha	Jagoran Kampani
1.	<i>2effect Empire</i>	Kano	1. Sani Musa Danja 2. Yakubu Muhammad
2.	<i>Abnur Entertainment</i>	Kano	1. Abubakar Bashir Maishadda 2. Nura M. Inuwa
3.	<i>ASMASAN Motion Pictures</i>	Jos	Sadik Sani Sadin
4.	<i>Crown Studio</i>	Kaduna	Ahmad Zango
5.	<i>DORAYI Mobies</i>	Kano	Falalu A. Dorayi
6.	<i>FKD Production</i>	Kano	Ali Nuhu
7.	<i>Hanan Synergy Concept</i>	Kano	Hannatu Bashir
8.	<i>Hikima Multimedia</i>	Kano	Aminu Ladan Abubakar (ALA)
9.	<i>Iyan Tama Film Production</i>	Kano	Alhaji Hamisu Lamido Iyan Tama
10.	<i>Mai Kwai Mobies</i>	Kano	
11.	<i>Maifata Pictures Jos</i>	Jos	Hamza Talle Maifata
12.	<i>Nafs Entertainment</i>	Kano	Nafisa Abdullahi
13.	<i>Rite Time Multimedia</i>	Kano	
14.	<i>RK Studio</i>	Kano	Dan'azumi Baba Chediyar 'Yar Gurasa
15.	<i>SAIRA Mobies</i>	Kano	Aminu Saira
16.	<i>Sauki Firm Production</i>	Sokoto	Alhaji Yahaya Maikaset Sokoto

Madogara: An samu waɗannan daga hirar da aka yi da masu kallon finafinan Hausa. Sannan an bi wasu hanyoyi domin tabbatarwa da suka haɗa da bincike a kafon intanet.

La'akari da waɗannan kampunan samar da finafinan Hausa, da ma sauransu da ba a kawo ba, ya kyautu a ce finafinan da ake samarwa sun kasance masu inganci tare da isar da ire-iren sakonnin da ake bukata zuwa ga rukunin jama'ar da ake bukata.

3.0 Hoton Fikrar Hausawa Cikin Finafinan Hausa

Kamar yadda bayanai suka gabata a sama, a zahirance kwaƙwalwar mai kallon fim na karkata ne kan irin al'ummar da wannan fim ke wakilta. Yazdani ya rawaito Mark yana cewa:

Whether we like it or not, our most profound thoughts and most intimate secrets, are now constantly expressed and experienced via moving pictures on screens big and small. (Mark in Yazdani ND: 21).

Fassara

Ko mu yarda ko kar mu yarda, a yanzu ana nuna mafi girman tunaninmu da sirrukanmu a kan fuskar talabishin a matsayin hotuna masu motsi manya da kanana.

Lura da wannan, a cikin finafinan Hausa ana so ne a ga Hausawa ta fuskokin da suka haɗa da:

- i. Launin fata

- ii. Harshe
- iii. Al'ada da dabi'a
- iv. Muhalli
- v. Falsafa da da ra'ayi da kuma salon tunani

A yayin da finafinan Hausan ke kofarin fito da wadannan abubuwa, har ila yau ana kyautata zaton su kasance masu mayar da hankali zuwa ga ɓangarorin rayuwar Bahaushe da suka kasance masu kyau domin daukaka matsayinsa a idon duniya. Abin tambaya a nan shi ne, ko yaya abin yake a finafinan Hausa?

Mafi yawan binciken da aka gudanar game da finafinan Hausa, suna nuni ga gazawar su wurin cimma manufofin da aka gina su a kai. Tuni dai wasu daga cikin marubuta suka nuna rashin yarda da iƙirarin masu shirya finafinan Hausa cewa suna wa'azantarwa. Al-Kanawy, 2004: 372) tambaya ya yi da cewa: "Wai ma a wace duniya marar sani ya taɓa wa'azantar da mutane?"

Chamo na da irin wannan ra'ayi, inda yake ganin hoton tarbiyyar Bahaushe cikin finafinan Hausa abu ne na tir da Allah wadai. Ya ce: "Wani muhimmin ɓangare na al'ada kuma shi ne tarbiyya... sai ga shi a finafinan Hausa ba a amfani da wannan tarbiyya." (Chamo, 2004: 385).

A ɓangare guda kuma, masu kallon finafinan Hausa da dama ba su gamsu da tsarin finafinan ba. A hirar da aka yi da Anas Sulaiman Darazo, ya bayyana cewa: "Nakan kalli tallen finafinan Hausa sosai, amma ba na kallon su karan kansu finafinan domin kayan ɓacin rai ne. Idan na tashi kallon fim ɗin Hausa, to na barkwanci nake kallo. Shi da ma na san ba ilimi na je kallo ba, kawai dai in ga shiririta ne."³

Daga cikin masu hannu a harkar finafinan Hausa ma akwai wadanda ke da ra'ayin cewa, kwalliya ba ta biyan kuɗin sabulu dangane da finafinai da dama. Alhaji Ahmad Ado Gidan Dabino ya bayyana: "A matsayinmu na 'yan fim, alkalanci ba na mu ba ne. Alkalanci ba namu

³ Ko bayan Anas ma, akwai masu kallon finafinan Hausa da dama da suka yi irin wannan furuci. Misali, Mujahed Mukhtar ya bayyana cewa: "Ai da ma akan kalli fim ɗin Hausa ne ba don a karu ba, sai domin a kashe lokaci." Koma dai yaya abin ya kasance, haƙiƙa akwai alamar tambaya kan ingancin finafinan, musamman yayin da aka yi la'akari da karuwar irin wadannan korafe-korafi da ke nuna rashin ingancinsu.

ba ne.” Sai dai duk da haka, ya tabbatar da: “... kuma na sha faɗa cewa akwai kura-kurai; babu wakilcin al’adu da addininmu a wasu finafinan. A wasu kuma akwai”⁴ (Gidan Dabino, 2018).

Dangane da daga darajar al’umma da kasa gaba daya, Gidan Dabino na ganin cewa, kafin a samu irin wannan wakilai nagari a cikin finafinai, dole ne sai masu shirya finafinan sun san mene ne shi kansa fim da kuma me yake tallatawa. Sannan dole sai sun san ita kasar kanta da abin da take ciki, da kuma abin da duniya take ciki. Ya bayyana cewa: “Su kansu masu fim din ma ba su san kasarsu ba, balle su san darajarta.” Sai dai a bangare guda kuma ya ce: “Su kuma hukumomin kasar me suke yi wa ‘yan kasar da har za su san kasar? Ba za ka samu kishin kasa da kula da kasa a zukatan ‘yan kasa ba sai ita kasar ta san darajarsu, ta san mutuncinsu kuma tana kula da su; sai su yi abu iya rai da mutuwa.”⁵

4.0 Sakamakon Bincike

Shin finafinai suna da tasiri a kan tunanin al’umma?

Wannan bincike bai ci karo da wani aikin da ya gabata ba da ke musanta tasirin finafinai ga tunani ‘yan Adam. Binciken ya gano cewa, finafinai suna da matuƙar tasiri kan tunanin al’umma da ma rayuwarsu ta gaba daya. Akwai masana da dama da ke da wannan ra’ayi, kamar yadda suka bayyana a ayyukansu mabambanta. Pirkis, Blood, Francis, da McCallum (2005) sun bibiyi irin waɗannan rubuce-rubuce na manazarta, kamar dai yadda aka bayyana a baya. Sakamakon binciken nasu ya tabbatar da wannan tasiri na finafinai kan rayuwar al’umma.

A bangare guda kuma, hirar da aka yi da wasu daga cikin Hausawa masu kallon finafinai (da suka haɗa da na ketare da kuma na Hausa) na kara tabbatar da tasirin finafinan kan rayuwar al’umma. Maikwari (2018) yana cewa:

⁴ Iyan-Tama ma na da irin wannan ra’ayi inda ya bayyana rawa da waka a matsayin hanyar “shashantar da zuciyar” ta hanyar kawo ayar Alkur’ani inda Allah ke cewa: “*Da mawaka, waɗanda ba bu bin su (mai taka rawarsu) face wawaye gafalallu* (26:224) (Iyan-Tama, 2004: 428).

⁵ Idan muka duba waɗanannan maganganu za mutarar da cewa, matsalolin finafinan Hausa a yau, sai dai a ce tsakanin gwamnati da masu shirya finafinan “kowane allazi da nasa amanu.”

A da lokacin da Hausawa ba su waye da kallon finafinai ba, sukan yi wasannin gargajiya ne na motsa jiki da kuma tatsuniyoyi da makamantansu. Lokacin da kallace-kallacen finafinai ya yi kamari tsakanin Hausawa, a lokacin ne kuma ayyukan ta'addanci suka ci gaba da yawaita. Idan muka duba salo da tsarin wadannan ayyukan ta'addanci, za mu ga daidai suke da wadanda ake nunawa a finafinan da muke kallo. To kuwa lallai "Da walakin goro a miya." (Maikwari, 2018)⁶

Lura da wannan, finafinai ba abu ne da ya kamata a zuba musu ido ko a bar su kara zube ba. Ya zama wajibi a fahimci tasirinsu da matsayinsu, tare da sarrafa su ta yadda za su kasance masu amfani ga cigaban tattalin arziki da zaman lafiya da ilimin kasa.

Yaya farfaganda take a cikin finafinan ketare?

Bincike ya tabbatar da cewa, tuni finafinan ketare suka yi kamari wurin amfani da wannan babbar dama domin yaƙar tunanin al'umma. Kamar yadda aka gani a sama, akwai ɓangarori na musamman da irin waɗannan finafinai suka karkata. Sun haɗa da nuna ƙarfin soja da nuna basira da fikira da dai makamantansu. Ko ba komai, yin hakan yana tasiri ga zukatan da dama daga cikin masu kallo.

A hirar da aka yi da wasu daga cikin masu kallon irin waɗannan finafinai, binciken ya fahimci cewa farfaganda tana tasiri kan al'ummar da ke kallo, ciki har da Hausawa. Wannan ne kuma ya sa ake sha'awar zuwa irin waɗannan ƙasashe. Finafinan sun lulluɓe aibun da za a iya samu a can da suka haɗa da hulɗa da haramtattun ƙwayoyi da taɓarbarewar tarbiyya da zinace-zinace da fyade da makamantansu. A maimakon haka, hoton ɓangaren rayuwa mai kyau kuma abar burgewa ne ya zanu a zukatan masu kallo.

Yaya hoton fikirar Hausawa yake a cikin finafinan Hausa?

Duk da cewa akwai daidaiƙun finafinan Hausa da ke nuna fikirar Hausawa tare da daga darajarsu, za a iya cewa "ba yadda aka so ba, ɗan fari ya faɗa a wuta." Sakamako daga finafinan da aka nazarta da kuma mutanen da aka yi hira da su, na nuna cewa finafinan Hausa ba su cika mayar da hankali kan ƙoƙarin ɗaukaka matsayin Hausawa a idon duniya ba. Za a iya kallon wannan ta ɓangarori da dama da suka haɗa da:

⁶ Hira da Malam Haruna Umar Maikwari, ɗan kimanin shekaru 36 da ke kallon finafinan Hausa da kuma na ketare.

- i. Rashin ba wa ‘yan sanda da jami’an tsaro matsayin da ke nuni da kaifin basira da jarunta da jajircewa a kan aiki bisa gaskiya.
- ii. Rashin nuna kyawawan halaye da suka hada da taimakon juna da son zaman lafiya da kishin kasa da ciyar da ita gaba tare kuma da neman ilimi da aiki da shi.⁷
- iii. Rashin nuna bunƙasar Hausawa a ɓangaren ilimin tattalin arziki da kimiyya da fasaha da kiyon lafiya. Wanda hakan ne zai sa a ga su ma al’umma ce da ta isa a tsoma baki da ita yayin da ake maganar cigaba a duniyar yau.
- iv. Rashin wani ƙoƙari na a-zo-a-gani domin ƙaryata sukar da ake yi wa Musulunci da Musulmai ta hanyar danganta duk waɗansu ayyukan ta’addanci zuwa gare su.
- v. Rashin wani ƙoƙari na a-zo-a-gani kan shirya fina-finai masu jigon gyaran tarbiyya, da ilimantarwa da wayar da kai da cusa kishin kasa da isar da muradun gwamnati da makamantansu.

Ra’ayin mafi yawan mutanen da wannan bincike ya tuntuɓa, yana nuna cewa, da dama daga cikin masu kallon fina-finan Hausa ba sa samun gamsuwar da suke tsammani daga fina-finan. Mafi yawan korafe-korafen da ake samu dangane da fina-finan Hausa sun shafi:

- i. Kauce wa al’adu da dabi’u na Bahausha tare da ikirarin su ake nunawa a cikin fina-finan;
- ii. Ƙarancin fasaha ga labaran da ake gina fina-finan a kansu;
- iii. Yawaitar satar labaran fina-finan ƙetare⁸; da
- iv. Bata lokaci a wuraren da ba su dace ba.⁹

5.0 Shawarwari

⁷ A hira da aka yi da Mujaheed Mukhtar, ya bayyana cewa: “Fina-finan Hausa sun fi gina labaransu kan soyayya. Sun kauce wa abin da ke faruwa a rayuwar Bahausha ta zahiri.”

⁸ Alhaji Ado Ahmad Gidan Dabino ya nuna cewa, akwai fina-finan Hausa da dama waɗanda daga kwafi ne na fina-finan ƙetare musamman Indiya: “Ka ga wanda zai dau wannan ya yi, da ma ba ma tallen al’adarsa yake yi ba” Hira da aka yi da Gidan Dabino, (2018).

⁹ Masu kallon fina-finan Hausa da dama sun yi irin wannan korafi na bata lokaci a wuraren da ba su dace ba. A hira da aka yi da Mujaheed Muhammad Manga, ya bayyana cewa: “Daya daga cikin matsalolin fina-finan Hausa shi ne bata lokaci. Komai sai a ce sai an nuna shi, ko da kuwa ya dace a wurce wurin, a bar mai kallo ya kiyasta abin da ya faru cikin ransa. Misali, za ka ga an nuna wani jarumi ko jaruma zai je wani wuri daga gidansa. Sai an haska yadda ya fito daga gidan, da yadda ya je wurin mota, da yadda ya buɗe motar, da yadda ya tayar ta, da yadda ya fita daga gidansa... Wannan bata lokaci ne kawai, wanda kamata ya yi a nuna abubuwa masu mihimmanci kawai, waɗanda ke isar da saƙonni na musamman ga masu kallo.”

Takardar ta tanadi wasu shawarwari bayan nazartar halin da finafinan Hausa suke ciki da kuma yadda abin ya kasance a finafinan ketare:

1. Ya kamata gwamnati ta sanya hannu cikin harkar finafinan Hausa tare da taka rawa ta bangarori da dama. Wannan ya haɗa da samar da muhimman jigogi da suka shafi tsaron kasa da tattalin arziki da zaman lafiya da haɗin kai, wanda zai kasance cikin finafinai dauke da salo mai jan hankali domin hannunƙa mai sanda da faɗakarwa ga al'umma. A bangare guda kuma, gwamnatin za ta taka rawa wajen tallafa wa harkar shirya finafinan, tare kuma da sanya ido a harkar domin tace gura-gurbi da bata gari.
2. Masu hannu cikin harkar shirya finafinai su yi karatun ta-natsu dangane da farfagandar fim a duniyar yau. Su dauki hanyoyi mafiya kyau na samar da kyakkyawar wakilcin Hausawa da ma kasa baki daya ga idon duniya.
3. Masu shirya finafinan Hausa su dukufa wurin yin bincike lokaci zuwa lokaci dangane da ra'ayin al'umma game da shirye-shiryensu, tare kuma da neman shawarwarin wuraren da ke buƙatar kwaskwarima ko sauyi. Wannan zai sa finafinan su kasance masu gusar da kishirwar Hausawa da ke kai su ga fafutukar neman finafinan ketare a koyaushe.
4. Masu shirya finafinan Hausa su bi sahun takwarorinsu na kasashen ketare wurin neman hanyoyin bunƙasa harkar. Wannan ya haɗa da inganta labaransu, da neman masu sanya hannun jari da kuma sanya jarumai masu bajinta a wuraren da suka kamata, da dai makamantan waɗannan.
5. A jawo masana da suka haɗa da farfesoshi da daktoci cikin harkar fim domin ba da shawarwari managarta da za su kai ga magance korafe-korafen da aka daɗe ana yi dangane da koma-bayan finafinan Hausa.

6.0 Kammalawa

Binciken masana da manazarta da suka gabata, waɗanda ke nuna dangantaka ta kai tsaye tsakanin tunanin al'umma da finafinai sun kai matuƙa da ya kamata duk wani mai hannu cikin shirya finafinan Hausa ya yi karatun ta-natsu. Yayin da aka yi kokarin toshe gurabun da mafi yawan masu kallo ke korafi game da su, akwai kyakkyawar zaton kwalliya za ta biya kuɗin sabulu, wanda a sannan ne za a cimma muradun da ake ta iƙirarin an gina finafinan ne kansu (ilimantarwa da faɗakarwa da kuma nishadantarwa). Idan ba a samu wannan gyara ba, yayin da

masu hannu cikin shirya fina-finan ke ganin suna abin yabo, ‘yan kallo sai dai su ci gaba da faɗin “da ma gwano ba ya jin warin jikinsa.”

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Wafanda Aka Yi Hira Da Su

Alhaji Ahmad Ado Gidan Dabino – Ranar Lahadi, 23 ga watan Disamba, shekarar 2018

Anas Sulaiman Darazo – Ranar Laraba, 7 ga watan Nuwamba, shekarar 2018

Malam Haruna Umar Maikwari – Ranar Asabat, 28 ga watan Oktoba, shekarar 2018

Mujaheed Muhammad Manga - Ranar Laraba, 7 ga watan Nuwamba, shekarar 2018

Mujaheed Mukhtar - Ranar Laraba, 7 ga watan Nuwamba, shekarar 2018

Rataye

Samfurin tambayoyin da aka yi amfani da su yayin tattaunawa da masu kallon finafinan Hausa da na kassashen ketare.

1. Shin kana kallon finafinan Hausa da kuma na ketare?
2. Shin abin da ake nunawa a cikin finafinai na da tasiri kan tunanin al'umma?
3. Ko ka taba cin karo da wani misali na tasirin finafinai kan wani mutum ko wasu mutane?
4. Shin finafinai sun yi tasiri ko suna tasiri ga rayuwarka?
5. Ko ka san ma'anar farfaganda cikin finafinai?
6. Shin a iya saninka masu shirya finafinan ketare na amfani da farfaganda cikin finafinansu?
7. Shin farfagandar finafinan ketare na iya tasiri kan tunanin masu kallo?
8. Shin farfagandar finafinan ketare ya taba yin tasiri a kanka?
9. Ko ka taba cin karo da wani misali na tasirin farfagandar finafinan ketare kan wani mutum ko wasu mutane?
10. Yaya kake ganin hoton Hausawa kamar yadda ake nuna su cikin finafinan Hausa?
11. Shin akwai kura-kuren da kake kallon ana samu cikin finafinan Hausa?
12. Shin akwai bangarorin da kake ganin suna bukatar a bunkasa su game da finafinan Hausa?